

UTILIZATION OF THERMAL ANALYSIS
IN DETERMINING THE AMOUNT OF POLYMER IN COMPOSITES
AND THE EXTENT OF PRE-POLYMERIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) as well as thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) techniques were used to study the internal structure of some dental composites. The amount of inorganic filler as well as the degree of pre-polymerization were obtained for a set of anterior and posterior dental restorative composites. The distinction among the characteristics of the polymerization behaviour of the two types of dental composites was revealed by DSC techniques and correlated to their use.

INTRODUCTION

In light of recent advances in the understanding of the microstructure of dental composites and the reactions governing their setting, several new formulations have been developed and even marketed as posterior restoratives. These were so claimed that they can be used as a reasonable substitute of dental amalgams as they possess comparable physical and mechanical properties. The final physical and mechanical properties of a composite restorative material is directly related to the chemical composition of the dental monomer system, the degree of its conversion to polymer and the ratio of the inorganic filler to the organic polymer matrix.

Previous workers have used infrared (Ir) and nuclear magnetic resonance (nmr) techniques to assess the degree of polymer conversion [1-2]. They based their evaluation on the ratio of the monomer absorptions at $\sim 1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ arising from the C = C bond remaining in the polymer infrared spectrum or the chemical shift of protons involved in the polymerization process in the nmr spectra [3-4].

Due to difficulties in infrared handling techniques of the composite, some workers standardized a differential scanning calorimetry DSC technique to evaluate the extent of polymerization of dental resins. This is based on measuring the amount of heat released during the polymerization process and comparing it to a theoretical value when the material is fully polymerized [5].

In the present work, some commercially available anterior and posterior dental resins of methacrylate base were subjected to thermal analysis in order to assess:

- a- The ratio of the inorganic filler to the organic resin present in the matrix.
- b- The amount of enthalpy, i.e. the heat liberated during polymerization.
- c- To correlate this heat to the ratio of the pre-polymerized material included in the reaction.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used in this study are listed in table (1).

Table 1
Materials used in this study and their sources

Classification	Material	Manufacturer
A. Anterior Composites	Conscice	3 M Dental Products Saint Paul, Minnesota
	Cosmic	AD International Limited London, England
	Biogloss	Detrey Dentsply Surrey, England
B. Posterior Composites	Epolite 100	G.C. Dental Industrial Corp Tokyo, Japan
	Isomolar	Vivadent Schaan- Liechtenstein
	P10	3 M Dental Products Saint Paul, Minnesota

A- Differential Scanning Calorimetric Measurements.

A Heraeus TA 500 differential scanning calorimeter fitted with a Pt-100 thermocouple was used in this study. The composite resins were mixed according to the manufacturer instructions. Samples (approximately 10 mg) were placed in a DSC aluminum pan and were quickly transferred within 5 sec. to the sample holder of the instrument. All polymerization experiments were conducted isothermally at 26°C under nitrogen gas. The instrument was calibrated using indium, ΔH (melting) = 6.98 cal g⁻¹, m.p. 156°C. The sample weight was obtained by subtracting the weight of the pan from the final weight after the run. The heat of polymerization was evaluated from the measurement of the total area of exothermic peak in the DSC curves. The area under the curve was calculated using the standard cutting and weighing technique. A base line for the DSC curve was obtained by a second measurement of the polymerized material under the same conditions.

At least 3 samples of each composite resin were measured in the same manner.

B- Thermogravimetry Measurements (TGA)

Dynamic thermogravimetry measurements were produced by a Heraeus TGA 500 thermobalance fitted with a Pt-Rh-Pt thermocouple. Weight of sample was about 50 mg and the temperature range extended from 30°C to 700°C. The heating rate was kept at 10 K/min and the sensitivity was 2 μ g/cm.

Results and Discussion

Figure (1) shows representative examples of the isothermal differential scanning thermal curves starting in each case at the interval of mixing of both the polymer and catalyst.

Fig. 1 The heat evolved from anterior (Cosmic) and posterior (P-10) composites.

Exothermic peaks has evolved, however distinct differences among the two composite types were noticed in the shape of these exothermic peaks. The posterior composites (Isomolar and P10) showed a rather

broad peak with a long tailing period until it reached the base line after 15 minutes for Isomolar, and 31 minutes for P10. The start of the exotherm was noticed after 2 minutes from the interval of the mix. The reaction maxima was reached at about 6 minutes.

However, the reaction of Isomolar appeared as if it is composed of two stages and the rate of polymerization looked rather slow at the first two minutes of the reaction.

The anterior composites had a similar retention time for the start of the reaction ranging from 2.5- 3.5 minutes, however the reaction reached its maximum enthalpy evolution at a shorter time than that of the posterior composites ranging between 4 minutes for Cosmic and 5.5 minutes for Biogloss. The reaction duration of anterior composites was rather shorter compared to the posterior ones as it reached the base line in about 13-16 minutes. These parameters are shown in table (2).

Table 2

Differential Scanning Calorimetric Results of Dental Composites

Material	Onset of reaction (min)	Duration of reaction (min)	Interval maximum reaction rate (min)
<u>A. Anterior</u>			
Consise	3	15	5
Cosmic	2	13	4
Biogloss	3.5	16	5.5
<u>B. Posterior</u>			
Epolite 100	4.5	12	5.5
Isomolar	3	15	6
P10	2	31	5.5

A. Determination of the Amount of the Inorganic Filler.

The amount of organic polymer within the matrix was evaluated by using TGA technique. The sample was heated up to 700°C and the loss of weight was determined from the produced thermal curve (figure 2).

Fig. 2 Thermogravimetric curves of two representative dental composites.

The weight loss ranged from 11.6 to 25.2%. Table (3) shows the % of the polymer in the matrix.

Table 3

Thermogravimetric Analysis Results of Different Composites

Material	% of polymer	% of filler	Starting of the decomposition(°C)
<u>A. Anterior</u>			
Concise	14.0	86.0	360
Cosmic	11.6	88.4	360
Biogloss	16.1	83.9	360
<u>B. Posterior</u>			
Epolite 100	19.2	80.8	390
Isomolar	25.2	74.8	350
P10	12.3	87.7	354

The composites when heated showed thermal stability up to (350°C) where signs of deviation from the base line started to appear due to weight loss of the organic constituents of the matrix (i.e. the polymer).

B. Determination of Enthalpy and Extent of Polymerization

The enthalpy was determined by measuring the area under the DSC curve. The amount of heat enthalpies varied among the different brands of composites. Table (4) shows the heat evolved in cal/gm.

Table 4
Amount of Heat Evolved and The Extent of Pre-Polymerization
Produced for the Different Dental Composites.

Material	ΔH for composite (Cal/g)	ΔH for polymer (Cal/g)	E.P.% (extent of polymerization)	E.P.P%* (extent of pre- polymerization)
A. Anterior				
Concise	4.42	31.57	42.6	56.4
Cosmic	4.38	37.75	50.9	48.1
Biogloss	5.26	32.67	44.1	54.9
B. Posterior				
Epolite 100	3.92	20.41	27.5	71.5
Isomolar	2.58	10.23	13.8	85.2
P10	3.77	30.65	41.3	57.7

* based on 99% polymerization.

The amount of heat evolved from the polymer was calculated using the percentage values obtained by the TGA as well as the values produced by DSC curves of the composites.

C. Determination of the Amount of Prepolymerized Material

The extent of polymerization (E.P.) was calculated using the equation proposed by previous workers [6]. The amount of heat evolved when 100% conversion has taken place was produced by the equation

$$\Delta Q_t = \frac{2 \cdot \Delta Q_0}{100} \left(\frac{100 - X}{M_b} + \frac{X}{M_t} \right)$$

Where M_b and M_t are the molecular weights of the polymers thought to be present in the matrix. The average molecular weight estimated in our case is 399; i.e. 0.5 Bisphenol A- glycidyl-methacrylate (Bis-GMA) M.wt. 512

and 0.5 Triethylene glycol dimethacrylate (TEGDMA) M.wt.286 and ΔQ_0 is the heat of polymerization of the methacrylate monomer. The calculated heat of polymerization to evolve when 100% polymerization is accomplished is 74.11 cal/gm.

It is well established that when the polymerization is carried out until completion the residual monomer does not exceed 1% and the average extent of polymerization is greater than 99% [7]. The following equation was developed to produce the extent of pre-polymerization in the samples:

$$E.P.P = 99 - \left[\frac{\Delta H_C \times 100}{W_p \times \Delta Q_t} \right]$$

where ΔH_C = heat evolved under the peak

W_p = percentage of polymer in the composite.

The results showed that the extent of pre-polymerization in the posterior composites was more than that of the anterior ones. This would justify the type of application, as the posterior composite has to confront more stresses. Nevertheless, posterior composites took more time to completely polymerize and this is probably due to the type of the catalyst used.

CONCLUSIONS

With minor manipulation of the calculation methods, thermal analysis techniques, namely DSC and TGA proved to be very effective in determining the amount of pre-polymerization of the composite used as a dental filling material. The developed method was sensitive enough to show the difference between the different types of composites i.e. anterior and posterior ones.

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